

Primer sets for the amplification of RTBV DNA.

Sequence sense and antisense	Amplifying region (bp positions)	PCR product size (bp)
Set 1		
5'-TGGTATCAGAGCGATGTCG-3' 5'-TCAGAGGTTGAATCTTGGGT-3'	1-1052	1052
Set 2		
5'-AGTGGAAAGTAGTTCAGCAGG-3' 5'-TTCATTCCCATCTAGGTGTG-3'	893-1740	848
Set 3		
5'-GCCGGTTGTGGAGTGTCTA-3' 5'-TCTACCATCCATCCAAGACC-3'	1471-2718	1248
Set 4		
5'-GGTCTTGGATGGATGGTAGA-3' 5'-GCTGAGGTGCTACATAGGTT-3'	2669-4165	1467
Set 5		
5'-CCTGTGAAACCAATACTGC-3' 5'-ATGCTGCTGTTCTATGCCTG-3'	3596-4669	1074
Set 6		
5'-CAACAGCCAGACACGAACTT-3' 5'-CCAGCCTTCTTCTGACGCAT-3'	4271-5481	1211
Set 7		
5'-CAGATGCGTCAGAAGAAGGC-3' 5'-CAGTCCAGTATCCAGCTTCA-3'	5459-6612	1154
Set 8		
5'-AGAGTGCCTAACTAAGGTGC-3' 5'-TGTGGTGCAGGACATTGTGT-3'	6011-7169	1159
Set 9		
5'-CCTCGCTGGAACCTCAATGA-3' 5'-AAGACGACTACTCACTGACC-3'	6888-7522	635
Set 10		
5'-CAAGGTTCTGAAGGGCTAC-3' 5'-TTGGTATCCACACTAGCAGA-3'	6794-7891	1098
Set 11		
5'-GTACCGTCAGGCCGTGTTAT-3' 5'-GCTCCTGCTGAACTACTTCC-3'	7718-915	1200

PCR products resolved in 2% agarose gel, stained with ethidium bromide, and visualized by UV illumination. Lanes 1 and 13 = size markers (100-300 bp and 1000-3000 bp), respectively; lanes 2-12 = PCR products produced from amplification reactions using 11 primer sets (primer set 1 to primer set 11).

perature of 72 °C for 6 min. For primer sets 3, 4, and 7, amplifications were carried out for 38 cycles with a denaturation temperature of 94 °C for 1 min, annealing temperature of 43 °C for 1 min, and extension temperature of 72 °C for 5 min. A 50 µl oil overlay was used to prevent refluxing of the sample. Total nucleic acid extracts from infected and uninfected rice leaves were used as positive and negative controls, respectively, and examined by agarose gel electrophoresis.

Results of the amplification, the corresponding PCR products derived by using each primer set, are shown in the figure. Using these 11 sets of primers, we are now able to amplify any part of the RTBV genome from tungro-infected plant DNA extract. ■

Clonal propagation of thermosensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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A simple and reliable technique for clonal propagation of thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was developed. Mature seeds (735) of a TGMS line were dehulled, soaked in 75% ethanol for 1-3 s, and washed in running tap water for 10 min. Seeds were disinfected for 10 min in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution and then rinsed three times in sterile distilled water. The seeds were germinated in a 100-ml flask containing half strength Murashige and Skoog's (MS) (1962) medium with 0.6% agar and 1.5% sucrose. Shoot base segments (5 mm long) were excised under aseptic conditions from 2-wk-old seedlings. They were then cultured in flasks containing about 5.0 ml of agar-solidified MS medium supplemented with 2 mg benzylaminopurine (BAP)/liter and grown under 10/14-h light/dark (L/D) photoperiod at 25°C. After 4 wk of culture, proliferated shoots were counted, and then subcultured under the same conditions. The solidified MS medium with 0.1 mg naphthalene acetic acid (NAA)/liter was used for rooting.

Effect of cytokinins on shoot proliferation.^a

Phytohormone (2 mg/liter)	Initial shoots (no.)	First subculture		Second subculture		Third subculture	
		Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)	Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)	Shoots (no.)	Shoot proliferation (%)
Benzylamino- purine (BAP)	48	139	289.6	498	358.3	1632	327.7
Kinetin	38	74	194.7	184	248.6	475	258.2
Zeatin	73	101	138.4	189	187.1	430	227.5

^a Subculture interval = 4 wk.

The medium supplemented with BAP produces the best response for shoot proliferation (see table). A test of differ-

ent concentrations of BAP showed that 2 mg BAP/liter is optimum for shoot proliferation. When the concentration of

BAP is increased to 4 mg/liter, there are some shoots with abnormal plant type and unfavorable leaf color even though the proliferation rate is reasonably high. After getting enough shoots by subculture, the proliferated shoots can be separated and transferred onto rooting medium, on which almost all of the shoots grow roots. About 1,000 regenerated plantlets were transferred into soil in the summer. Visual observation showed all plants to be normal. ■

Greenhouse rearing and rating scale for rice mealy bug

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Rice mealy bug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger possesses behavioral attributes that made earlier attempts for mass-rearing in the greenhouse unsuccessful: a) at all stages (except crawler), the pests are sedentary and remain under the leaf sheath, making their handling tedious and time consuming; b) the soft-bodied females are sensitive to handling and do not settle on plants if disturbed; and c) insect longevity, fecundity, and population increase are

significantly influenced by host plant age.

Based on these observations, we developed a procedure for mass-rearing *B. rehi* in the greenhouse (see figure). Using an adhesive (Camilin), five gravid females were attached to the auricles of potted 60-d-old TN1 plants at the rate of one female/tiller. The plants were then covered with a mylar film cage (90 cm high, 10 cm diam). By 25 d after infesta-

tion (25 DAI), about 360 adult females were produced on each potted plant, and 5 d later, crawlers emerged. Gravid females collected from leaf sheaths were

Procedure for greenhouse rearing of rice mealy bug and screening of rice cultivars for resistance.

Reactions of rice varieties to *B. rehi* in the bulk seedling test.

Variety	Plant damage rating ^a	
Co 9	3	d
Co 18	1	e
Co 21	1	e
Co 22	1	e
Co 23	5	c
Co 25	7	b
Co 26	9	a
Co 27	9	a
Ptb18	9	a
Ptb21	1	e
Ptb33	3	d
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	a

^a Av of 5 replications. See text for definition of scale. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

